

The Modern City facing the future

Introduction

The intention of this paper is fourfold - first to outline present circumstances, second to scan the concept of the 'ideal', third to cite critical commentaries and finally to offer two 'models' and a provisional checklist for the future.

Present circumstances

In the evolution of architecture and urbanism, the C20 Modern Movement was unique for inventing the idea the future could be 'designed', and that the promise anticipated spiritually and physically improving conditions over those inherited. The optimism generated by this extraordinary intellectual and technical revolution was frustrated by events beyond the control of designers unable to harness the political, economic and social forces which shape our environment. The declarations emanating from this movement not only adopted an ethical stance, architecture being distinguished from the other arts through its social function, but assumed in a democratic age architecture and planning would actively help to shape new common, philosophical and social values, concerns for rational equality, light, air, hygiene, aspect, prospect, recreation and so on.

Although these could not be realised as coherent entities they did articulate visions that fuel frustration with an urban future increasingly projected in terms of remedial operations rather than visionary concepts. Idealism has yielded to economic power, political expediency and pragmatism, late free-market capitalism appearing reluctant to commit itself to any form of land settlement consistent with the production of an urban form in which its inhabitants can find coherence. In Plato's Republic it was recognised that the sum of a number of individually rational decisions results in collective chaos. The modern city has transpired as Tafuri's 'Tool of Capitalism'.

A critical review reveals fundamental flaws in the formal patterns promoted, and disjunction between the forms, social programmes and political means for realisation. In an age of liberal capitalism, with no proper framework for co-ordinating 'big' decisions with 'little' decisions, an anti-intellectual climate prevails, ideology appearing to have been displaced by ideas. As Pasqual Maragall, long-time mayor of Barcelona, stated: 'The lesson in humility that we ought to have derived from the overwhelming audacity of our collective pretensions is overwhelming'.

The programme espoused by the Modern Movement proposed harnessing the forces in society for the benefit of future generations, but wherein now lies that promise? Are its ethical ideals outdated, or can the social aspirations and humanist creeds be reformulated to inform a global, urban future? Alternative programmes must now be articulated, which exploit the partnership of political ambition and the dynamism of market forces, for the greater good. Our purpose as citizens and professionals should be to alleviate the physical conditions in those cities which have evolved as ghettos of economic greed and ecological disaster and to deliver the promise of urban centres as sources of inspiration and beauty, as places of social, cultural and intellectual development and joy.

The 'Ideal'

When problems are interpreted as crises, fear dominates, economics rule, technology becomes the 'panacea', values are sacrificed. Architecture provides a metaphysical clarity and renders the world less threatening. The city in history is associated with the desire to create life-enhancing, symbolically charged, memorable places.

Helen Rosenau devoted many years to exploration of the Ideal City:

"• The consistent striving for perfection is a clear indication of the recurrent human desire to attain a state in which conditioned necessity is replaced by liberty and harmony.

• The desire to attain a perfect physical environment and a more satisfying way of life is characteristic of Western Civilisation, since it possesses dynamic force and incorporates economic and social change and experiment.

• An ideal city represents a religious vision, or a secular view, in which social consciousness and the need of the population is allied with a harmonious conception of artistic unity.

• The perennial theme of art is an intensified vision regarding the quality of life and therefore the subject of ideal cities reaches right into the core of artistic creation.

- *It is characteristic of European history that the concern with merely formal matters recedes in time, and the social function of the city and its inhabitants demands growing expression.*
- *One has to distinguish between the solution of a particular problem in a perfect manner, and the creation of a prototype of a supranational normative character, an ideal plan."*

Since the C18, when Boullé and Ledoux celebrated the advent of Newtonian intellectual rationality with vast, geometrically pure monuments, there has been a tendency to try and overlap the issues of utopianism, and realism, to generate either a 'realistic utopianism' or a 'utopian realism'.

The evolution in utopian form throughout the late 19th and early 20th Centuries is characterised by a shift in the nature of their presentation. Having moved from the classical, discrete, geometrically stable ideal 'objects' through the paternalistic, post-industrial solutions proposed in the C19, an increasing secularisation and implementation of democracy became the format for the ideal in C20, from a centralised plan to a grid. Suddenly the boundaries of the imagery alter; instead of a clearly delineated utopia, framed by unspecified wasteland, there appear a series of proposals presented in a way that suggests implementation without boundary. The proposals suddenly appear as arbitrarily selected fragments of a much larger vision, the grid becoming a device very much associated with C20 urbanism.

The ideal models expose the extent to which formal arrangements were devised to express visions of social and ethical absolutes. Symbolism is a key, generating element linking Man to Nature and the Universe, the urbanism in each age reflecting cultural norms. As social programmes became more defined in C19 so its pragmatically orientated 'ideal' urban models eliminated symbolism and the expression emerged as form in the service of profit, the moral foci being work ethic and religion, the latter in C20 yielding to materialism.

Critiques of modern urbanism

The C18 saw Man as essentially rational but blinded by ignorance or superstition whereas in C20 we saw him as deeply irrational, held in check by reason. That reason took the form of what was deemed the certainty of science which, with art, formed an intellectual duality. Robert Maxwell has commented that: "City planning is a modern 'subject', but does it exist as a discipline? If so by what is it prescribed? Is it a science implying rational solutions based upon analytical concepts which may not last very long? Statistics have little effect on appearances - patterns of use are very different from patterns of analysis."

In Russia the urban experiments on a massive scale in the early thirties failed in spite of a centrist regime which could dictate and guarantee implementation - subject, however to political censorship. Ironically Moisei Ginzburg in 1928 commented to Le Corbusier:

"The unresolved deadlock of Western Functionalism is this; that it is prevented by the social structure it works under and the condition of work that these impose on the architect, from conceiving all individual problems as part of an organic whole ... This cannot be like our Constructivism when we see that outside and beyond the individual architect-loner in those societies there does not exist any kind of social force. There is no single social goal in those societies which can expand their Functionalism to become like our Constructivism ... We are approaching form, not as an end in itself but as a path towards the development of a social goal."

Guardini defined the dialectic of two philosophical worlds, the old world of the Platonic idea and the modern world of existential philosophy. Alan Colquhoun has elaborated this dialectic within the classifications of C20, cities as Process and cities as Form:

"The city as Process is noteworthy since the principles it supports can function regardless of its physical pattern - it is concerned with means rather than ends - a technological utopia within which symbolic and cultural roles are not prescribed - form is independent of function.

The City as Form - the formal city - is rule-laden and subject to the 'science' of urban aesthetics; it is legible and coherent and concerned with ends rather than means; it is elementalised such that discrete parts are related to each other; the symbolic and cultural attributes are historically devised."

These characteristics were critically examined in mathematical terms by Christopher Alexander in 1965 in a paper entitled 'The City is not a Tree', and applied to specific examples. He elaborated the distinction between 'artificial' cities and 'natural' cities, the first lacking some essential ingredient, the second having acquired the patina of everyday life. He likens these to analytical diagrams familiar to mathematicians the first a 'tree' and the second a 'semi-lattice' (Figure 1). These describe organisational patterns by means of sets, the 'set' being a collection of elements which we think of as belonging together. He states: "Since, as designers we are concerned with the physical, living city and its physical backbone, we restrict ourselves to considering 'sets' which are collections of material elements ... When the elements of a set belong together because they co-operate or work together, we call the set of elements a 'system'".

He then illustrated how such perceptions may be transferred to 'tree' and 'semi-lattice' diagrams taken from mathematics. When applied to cities the first eliminates complexity and with it social realities, the latter integrates the complexities of life as understood. He applied his analytical method to several cities, of which I will select only two which have been the subject of discussion at this conference:

"Chandigarh (Figure 2) - the whole city is served by a commercial centre in the middle, linked to the administrative centre at the head. Two subsidiary elongated, commercial cores are strung out along the major arterial roads. Subsidiary to these are further administrative community and commercial centres, one for each of the city's 20 sectors; the structure is a tree.

Brasilia (Figure 3) - the entire form pivots about the central axis, and each of the two halves is served by a single main artery. This main artery is in turn fed by subsidiary arteries parallel to it. Finally, these are fed by the roads which surround the super blocks themselves. The structure is a tree."

These two examples implemented the separation of functions posited by CIAM and that concept has thereby crystallised in our cities. A living, or natural city, he claims, when unconstrained by artificial conceptions, shows itself to be a semi-lattice.

He summarises his thesis as follows:

"When we think in terms of a 'tree' we are trading the humanity and richness of the living city for a conceptual simplicity which benefits only designers, planners, administrators and developers. Every time a piece of a city is torn out, and a 'tree' made to replace the 'semi-lattice' that was there before, the city takes a further step toward dissociation. In any organised object, extreme compartmentalisation and the dissociation of internal elements are the first signs of coming destruction."

Endorsing this thesis, Michael Waltzer has classified urban space into two distinct groups: 'single-minded' and 'open-minded' spaces. "Single-minded" describes a concept of urban space that has been designed for, and fulfils a single function; 'Open-minded' is conceived as multi-functional and has evolved or been designed for a variety of uses in which everyone can participate."

Turning now from the City as Process to the city as Form, a critique was offered by Colin Rowe in 1979. He characterised the modern city as displaying an extraordinary addiction to towers and unconstructed

spaces which concepts are characterised by 'physics envy', 'zeitgeist worship', 'object fixation' and 'stradaphobia'.

- 'Physics Envy' is "a state of mind, the idea that architecture could ever be elevated, or reduced, to that most certain of sciences";
- 'Zeitgeist Worship' refers to modern architecture's apologetic, "the conception of the architect as sensitive antenna, humble pencil, obedient planchette, just simply transcribing the mutterings and utterings of the 'spirit of the age'";
- 'Object Fixation' comments on the pre-occupation of modern architecture with the 'outer angle', in other words the tradition of modern architecture to produce objects rather than spaces - how then, he asks "to make a city if all the buildings proclaim themselves as objects; and how many object/buildings can be aggregated before comprehension fails?";
- 'Stradaphobia' describes the privileging of vehicular movement as the controlling armatures generating modern urbanism devised by "incompletely educated highway engineers".

He summarises the failure of modern urbanism as "'space shyness' ... the city as an accumulation of solids in a largely unmanipulated void".

And then there is the grid, a universal C20 planning device described by Rosalind Krauss as: "the form that is ubiquitous in the art of our century". The seductive power of the grid as a hypothetical planning solution may be partly explained by its very abstraction; she avers: "the grid conveyed one of the basic laws of knowledge - the separation of the perceptual screen from that of the real world". The edges of the images allow their central imagery to fade into undefined obscurity, leaving just enough information to imply infinite extension, witness Garnier's Cité Industrielle.

In the 'Broadacre City' of Frank Lloyd Wright a grid is implicated which is to be laid across the whole of the United States, an instrument of anti-urban ideology as with the Garden City planners and Soviet Decentralists. Corbusier, on the other hand, employs the grid as an ordering device: "Man, by reason of his very nature, practices order". The idea of the grid as an ordering device was taken to its extreme in the work of Superstudio, who proposed the establishment of a global Cartesian grid attaining, as Colin Rowe describes it, "the final emancipation from the tyranny of objects". But a question for this century is, once the grid has been instituted as a framework for ideal planning, is it possible to develop it further? The implications are ultimately democratic and utilitarian, but as Krauss states: "once the grid appears, it seems quite repellent to change ... we have discovered that one of the most modernist things about it is its ca-

capacity to serve as a paradigm or model for the anti-developmental, the anti-narrative, the anti-historical".

Future Cities

Alvin Toffler in 'Future Shock' called attention to three basic features of planning in industrial nations: "an obsession with economics to the exclusion of all other concerns; a time bias which regards five years as long range; an elitist character that removes decisions from the ordinary citizen and hands them to remote experts and bureaucrats".

He elaborates three declarations which I summarise:

Economics Alone Cannot Solve The Crisis

- 'fixed growth rates' and 'full employment' cannot be treated as independent goals
- the crisis cannot be solved by mortgaging the future for the sake of short term gains;
- the idea of a quick economic 'fix' is as dangerous as the notion of a quick, neat technological 'fix';
- economic policies must be combined with compatible policies dealing not only with money supply, wages, prices and balance of payments but also resource use, environment, education, cultural life, transportation, communications etc;

The Past Cannot (and should not) be Recaptured

- the old industrial order cannot be reinstated;

Every great crisis is also an opportunity.

- it is necessary to de-colonise the richest nations as well as the poorest;
- more radical conservation policies require more imagination in order to do more with less;

It is necessary, he concludes, to humanise technology and overhaul the creaking political institutions and imagine fresh personal and political priorities. Cities being the product of power are sustained or destroyed through the exercise of that power; we must, consequently, understand what is the nature of those forces and explore how they may be harnessed in the interests of sustainability.

Two examples are offered which provide evidence that a combination of invention combined with political will and understanding can fulfil not only the ideals which have attended urbanism through history but which are evolving as our global awareness matures. Barcelona is a city of 1.7 million people. It combines the attributes of both Process and Form. In 1999 the RIBA awarded this city its Royal Gold Medal for Architecture. I summarise the citation which stated Barcelona's rejuvenation resulted from:

- collective inspiration;
- a clear political and social agenda shared by

the city authorities, business interests, designers and citizens;

- an ambitious, pragmatic, urban strategy;
- transformation of the public realm, expanded amenities, regenerated economy, pride in its citizens and delight for visitors;
- historical buildings benefiting from refurbishment;
- past and present, work and play being intermeshed in a new totality;
- city planners demonstrating sensitivity to what buildings can do to shape the city and give it meaning.

A city of Process is Curitiba, the capital of Parana, which turns problems into sources of inspiration. As in Barcelona an inspirational mayor Jaime Lerner, who is also an architect, 30 years ago started an urban revolution. He gathered a team of creative professionals and developed solutions that were the product of extraordinary lateral-thinking, cost-effective, visually symbolic and politically astute decisions. They created the conditions for all citizens to contribute to a sustainable urban environment. The first Open University of the Environment is sited in a disused quarry, a magical, tree structure constructed of low energy materials. Each school class in Curitiba with its teacher spends a week in the University learning how small scale interventions contribute to the creation of practical benefits. Buildings in other spent quarries are destined to support a permanent festival of the arts. A cultural ethos is thereby evolved which colours every aspect of life in Curitiba. One astonishing innovation is the public transport system which is safe, swift and smart, low priced and is used by 75% of commuters, two million passengers a day, even though car ownership is higher than in São Paulo. Densities have been concentrated around bus stops and along routes, so land use planning and transport complement each other. Traffic has declined 30% since 1974 although the population has doubled. Appropriate technology has been employed to humanise the environment and the services which sustain life, each problem being solved as it arose, rather than being suffocated by the dogma of a master-plan.

These no doubt imperfect examples provide indication that political, social and economic awareness can be harnessed in the interests of citizens without sacrificing global interests. Whereas C20 imagery centred on the City as Form, the brief for the C21 city must, I contend, be stated in terms of Alan Colquhoun's City as Process. Further confirmation is provided by The Beijing Charter, presented in that city at the 20th Congress of the International Union of Architects in June 1999.

It states, the coming century calls for:

- “• a methodology that guides the architect through all aspects of the built environment;
- a fusion of architecture, landscape architecture and city planning;
- an architectural process which views construction, operation, maintenance, renewal and conservation as a whole;
- multiple technologies that are rooted in indigenous cultures and societies, and are extended to the realm of human feelings;
- regional initiatives that enhance visual and psychological identities;
- incorporation of fine art, craftsmanship and industrial design in architects' work;
- moral conduct that treats society as the ultimate client;
- an open and continuous education programme for professionals, clients and the wider public.”

The following items are offered as elaboration of those in the Beijing Charter and Barcelona's citation:

- the obvious must be perpetually repeated, that cities exist first and foremost to satisfy the social needs of communities;
- the conduct of C20 society was predicated on perpetual growth - this is a chimera and a mental adjustment to the reality of finite resources distributed for the greatest benefit of the greatest number is the ideal to which we should aspire;
- the planning of new urban centres must recognise that the bigger communities become, the greater the loss of social coherence;
- environmental conditions should be at the heart of decision-making at all levels, with environmental sustainability as the ethic of modern urban design;
- the planner must be an enabler, not a god;
- educational programmes must be adjusted to include teaching children and adults about their environment so as to equip them to participate in the process of respecting and improving their environment.
- there is a necessity to mobilise creative thinking in general, and among environmental professionals in particular;
- theory is indispensable - it is how we make sense of the world;
- an answer to the crucial question 'are materialism and sustainability antithetical or compatible?' must be consciously sought in the test-beds which are our urban environments, present and future;
- cities will retrieve quality not by returning to regressive ideologies of nostalgia but by liberating new energies of architectural invention;
- technology is not a panacea - it resembles Macaulay's comment on the imagination of a colleague that it

"resembled the wings of an ostrich - it enabled him to run but not to fly";

- the symbolism of public and social realms must be recovered;
- it is imperative that the urgency of resolving strategic objectives in sustainable form be resolved beyond pragmatism, to the level of spirituality which distinguishes architecture from building.

This encapsulation is neither revolutionary or original. It certainly is the case that the Grand Narratives of Progress and Enlightenment must now be adjusted to accommodate a revised agenda. The crucial question to ask as the memory of one century of frustrated ambition is replaced by the presence of another posing problems on a global scale is, what should be the legitimate role of the architect?

In 'Architecture and Disjunction', Bernard Tschumi poses the issue thus;

"Either we could ... 'conserve' our historical role as translators of, and form-givers to, the political and economic priorities of existing societies. Or we could function as critics and commentators of society through writings or other forms of practice ... Finally, we could act as revolutionaries by using our environmental knowledge in order to be part of professional forces trying to arrive at new social and urban structures."

He then asks:

"How could architects avoid seeing architecture and planning as the faithful product of dominant society, viewing their craft, on the contrary, as a catalyst for change? Could architects reverse the proposition and, instead of serving a conservative society that acted upon our cities, have the city itself act upon society? ... Could space be made a peaceful instrument of social transformation, a means of changing the relationship between the individual and society by generating a new lifestyle?"

The City of the Future will become the litmus paper of contemporary culture. FORM had its turn in C20 - now is the moment for PROCESS to benefit from the lessons conveyed by our flawed inheritance.

KEYWORDS

Urban, Form, Process, Future

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